

THE DIGITALIZING OF EDUCATION IN HIGH SCHOOLS: PROS AND CONS

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ABSTRACT

The modern world is constantly changing. Innovations are introduced into various spheres of human activity, which, on the one hand, orients people towards continuous development, improvement of their knowledge, skills, competencies, mastering new types of activities in related sectors of the economy. On the other hand, routine work is increasingly handed over to machines, and a person is required to be creative, willing to cooperate with colleagues in the search for new solutions, and - most importantly - the ability to critically evaluate the proposed information both for reliability and from the point of view of its logical embedding. to the current tasks. As it is known that digitalization has entered in all spheres of life, including education. The aim of the study presented in the article is to determine the positive and negative aspects of digital transformation in education system of Higher education. As a result of the study, not only the attitude towards digitalization was revealed, but also determined the identification of possible ways to develop digital tools for the implementation of the educational process.

Nowadays, the term "digitalization" gains more and more popularity, but only a few are able to correctly interpret its essence. Digitalization is not just the introduction of digital technologies in different areas of life to improve its quality, but also fundamental changes in thinking stereotypes and working methods [8]. To date, this kind of transformation has covered almost all areas of activity, including the field of education. Digital

technologies are a tool for the effective delivery of information and knowledge to the student, the creation of educational materials and an effective way of teaching, and most importantly, a means of building a new educational environment

Therefore, digitalization in a broad sense is understood as a modern global trend in the development of the economy and society, which is based on the transformation of information into digital

form, which should lead to an increase in the efficiency of the economy and an improvement in the quality of life.

However, it should be taken into account that digitalization in a broad sense can be considered as a trend of effective global development only if the digital transformation of information meets the following requirements: it covers production, business, science, the social sphere and everyday life of citizens; accompanied only by the effective use of its results; its results are available to users of the transformed information; its results are used not only by specialists, but also by ordinary citizens; users of digital information have the skills to work with it. This is a very important detail for understanding digitalization as a social phenomenon, since in no country in the world at the moment digital transformation has fully acquired such a form.

Digitalization has replaced computerization, during which it was mainly about the use of computer technology to solve certain economic problems. The great possibilities of digital representation of information lead to the fact that digitalization already forms integral technological environments of "habitat" (ecosystems, platforms), within which the user can create the friendly environment he needs in order to solve entire classes of tasks.

If we talk specifically about the digitalization of education, then it leads to serious changes in the labor market and is focused on reorganizing the educational process, rethinking the role of a teacher. On the one hand, digitalization undermines the methodological basis of the high school inherited from the past, which has proven

its effectiveness, but on the other hand, it creates the availability of information in its various forms (not only in text, but also in sound, visual). In addition to the availability of information, the digitalization of education implies a deeper study of the information received: virtual reality technologies, for example, create the possibility of using digital simulators, and mobile learning technologies allow you to study anywhere and at any time.

However, the availability of information will require teachers and students to constantly search for and select relevant and interesting content, as well as high-speed processing of the information received. And if students quickly adapt to the digital environment, forming the initial skills and abilities to use digital technologies, then this cannot be said about people of older generations. And since the digitalization of education directly depends on the level of mastery of digital technologies of the teacher, he must learn how to use the almost unlimited information resources provided by the Internet and new technological tools. Based on these ideas, we can talk about the completion of the informatization stage. Educational institutions of all levels are equipped with computers, teachers have been trained and retrained in the use of information technology (IT) in the educational process. The main areas of IT application in education are:

- development of pedagogical software for various purposes;
- development of websites for educational purposes;
- development of methodological and didactic materials;
- management of real objects;

- organizing and conducting computer experiments with virtual models;
- implementation of a targeted search for information [2, p. 50].

E. A. Kashina notes: "The requirements for the skills of students have changed, since it is necessary not only to read, write and count, you need to be able to organize data resources, cooperate fruitfully, collect, evaluate and use information" [7, p. 1].

Thus, we can talk about the need for a modern person to have an information culture as an element of human culture and as a prerequisite for a comfortable existence in society, and its formation is one of the most important tasks of the education system.

To solve it, adaptation to changing conditions and requirements was required. With the advent of the Internet in 1982, a virtual world is formed, filled with new connections, such as online games, social networks, connecting it with the real world. The real and virtual worlds are interdependent, and according to one of them, according to A. V. Keshelav [3, p. 5–6], a person can be identified. Their merger forms a hybrid world through which the vital actions of the real world are performed with the help of the virtual one. A prerequisite for this process is the effectiveness of information and communication technologies and the availability of digital infrastructure.

The digital revolution that has swept the world economy is impressive in its pace and scale. The transition from electronic computers to personal computers lasted decades, and now such global changes in technology occur in months. Initially, digitalization was reduced to the automation of technologies, the spread of the Internet, mobile communications,

social networks, the emergence of smartphones, the growth of consumers who used new technologies. However, very quickly, digital technologies are becoming part of the economic, political and cultural life of a person. Currently, digitalization has penetrated into education. Wiktionary reveals the content of the concept of "digitalization" as "a digital method of communication, recording, data transmission using digital devices" [14]. A. Marey considers digitalization as a change in the paradigm of communication and interaction with each other and society [9]. E. L. Vartanova, M. I. Makseenko, S. S. Smirnov clarify the content of this concept - this is not only the transfer of information into digital form, but a complex solution of an infrastructural, managerial, behavioral, cultural nature [3, p. 17]. That is, we can conclude that the development of the Internet and mobile communications are the basic technologies of digitalization. A promising task for all universities is to improve the skills of digital literacy teachers, focused not only on the development of courses, but also on the use of the digital environment in the educational process. The digital environment requires teachers to have a different mentality, a picture of the world, a completely different way and forms of work with students. Digital literacy is the ability to create and apply content through digital technologies, including computer programming, search, information exchange, and communication skills. Henry Jenkis, however, reveals the content of the concept of digital literacy as the ability to work with a computer like with iron, understanding the features of the device and distribution of digital information, the structure of the network community and

the features of social media [4]. Doot Belshaw defined the elements of digital literacy, such as understanding the cultural context of the Internet environment, the ability to communicate in online communities, create and distribute content, and self-develop [4]. The content of digital literacy comes down to the understanding that if there is clarity in the structure and content of digital reality, then there will be clarity in control and interaction with digital technologies.

Digitalization management is possible with common databases, learning effectiveness criteria, in other words, an integrated approach that would determine the goals, structures and content of the educational process. The Association "National Society for Technologies in Education" has developed various procedures for evaluating education by consumers, experts, and professional communities [12]. For example, an online course is credited to the student as part of the university curriculum.

Digitalization management in the educational environment is carried out with the help of digital marketing, aimed at organizing interaction with educational support staff, scientific and pedagogical workers, graduates, students, applicants using a range of digital communication channels; monitoring changes in the formation of a positive image of the university; stimulating the creation of new digital communities and innovations; development of personalized marketing materials for target audiences.

We see that the process of digitalization of the economy, education and any other spheres of human life involves the formation of a digital (information) culture in him, which allows him to competently

use the opportunities that open up and seamlessly integrate into the environment of the information society. At the same time, back in 1991, A. I. Rakitov formulated the following features:

- any individual, group of individuals, enterprise or organization anywhere in the country and at any time can receive for an appropriate fee or free of charge on the basis of automated access and communication systems any information and knowledge necessary for their life and solving personal and socially significant problems;
- society produces, operates and is available to any individual, group or organization modern information technology that ensures the feasibility of the previous paragraph;
- There are developed infrastructures that ensure the creation of national information resources in the amount necessary to support the constantly accelerating scientific, technological and social progress. Society is able to produce all the information necessary for life, and, above all, scientific;
- a process of accelerated automation and robotization of all spheres and branches of production and management is taking place in society;
- there are radical changes in social structures, the result of which is the expansion of the scope of information activities and services [13, p. 32–35].

Thus, the education system should provide society with a confident transition to the digital age, focused on productivity growth, new types of labor, human needs, which is possible through the inclusion of all segments of the population in the educational process, building individual learning routes, managing their own

learning outcomes, virtual and augmented reality [11, p. 248].

The digitalization of education involves the use of mobile and Internet technologies by students, expanding the horizons of their knowledge, making them limitless. The

productive use of digital technologies, the inclusion of students in an independent search, selection of information, participation in project activities forms their competencies of the XXI century.

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